

قرانيون (Qur'anists)

also known as "Kala-Kato"

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Abrahamic, Islam, Language, Arabic

Qur'anist religious groups popularly known as Kala-Kato (in the Hausa language) are some Muslim adherents that accept to act on the directives of the Qur'an alone, without making any reference to the tradition of the prophet Muhammad (SAW) or any other sources of the Islamic Shari'ah. The groups are mostly found in northern Nigeria affirmed to have emerged in the early 1980s, and extend to the present time. They were accused of some instances of religious violence in the region such as the Mai-Tasine crises, and the Kala-Kato crises of Bauchi etc. Their religious practices sound different from those of the Sunni and Shi'a followers, especially in the manner of ablution, prayer, and their likes, as they relied on the little glimpse made by the Qur'an on the religious duties. They often establish their separate mosques, and schools of the Qur'an and preach mostly at markets, roadsides and mosques to extend their ideologies. The group does not document ideas in books as they solely rely on the only book having divine origin (Qur'an).

Date Range: 1980 CE - 2000 CE

Region: Northern Nigeria.

Region tags: Nigeria, Northern Nigeria

Northern Nigeria is a region established in 1914 during the amalgamation of the protectorates and was further sub-divided after the independence to comprise several states: North Central - Benue, Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, and Plateau. North East - Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba, and Yobe. North West - Kaduna, Katsina, Kano, Kebbi, Sokoto, Jigawa, Zamfara.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Sani, Usman. "THE SCHOLARLY (OBJECTIVE), POLITICAL AND 'YAN KALA-KATO (THE MAN SAID) TRENDS OF TAFSIR IN NORTHERN NIGERIA." The Nigerian Association of Arabic and Islamic Studies Kano State Branch 1 (2013): 14–31.
- Source 2: Hassan, Ibrahim. "An Introduction to Islamic Movements and Modes of Thought in Nigeria." In Program of African Studies. LaRay Denzer and Rebecca Shereikis, 2015.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://jamestown.org/brief/briefs-146/>.

– Source 1 Description: Town, James . “NIGERIA’S IMAMS WARN OF THREAT FROM KALA KATO ISLAMIST MOVEMENT,” 2010.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.accord.org.za/ajcr-issues/religious-violence-in-nigeria/>

– Source 2 Description: Sampson, Isaac. “Religious Violence in Nigeria: Causal Diagnoses and Strategic Recommendations to the State and Religious Communities.” ACCORD, 2012.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://aminiya.ng/mu-ba-yan-kala-kato-ba-ne-yan-kuraniyun-ne-usman-yakubu/>

– Source 1 Description: Mustapha, Olusegun. “Mu ba ‘yan kala kato ba ne, ‘yan Kur’aniyun ne -Usman Yakubu.” Aminiya, 2015.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The group share cultural practices with the Sunni and Shi'a groups on the practices of prayer, fasting, and ablution with some differences in the manner and mode of practising.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The group preach mostly at markets, roadsides and mosques to recruit new members in the religious movement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The group does not recognise any modern political administration, hence they often criticise it for going against the guidance of the Qur'an.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group considered the application of any guidance rather than that mentioned by the Qur'an as a form of heresy.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: Apostates are left on their own since the group does not have the legal authority to prosecute any person in the society of the northern Nigeria.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 7000000

Notes: The members of the group are found in Borno, Kaduna, Kano Katsina and other states of the northern Nigeria.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 2

Notes: The members are the minority group in the region.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The group hold to the divine scripture of Islam (Qur'an) as the only source of guidance.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The scripture (Qur'an) was written in Arabic language.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The scripture is constantly recited to gain reward from Allah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The scripture was revealed to Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W) through the angel Jibril.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'an was inspired by Allah to the Prophet through Angel Jibril.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: They only build mosques for congregational prayer sessions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is iconography present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Spirit does not perish, while the material body decomposes after death.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The group's divine scripture referred to the belief in the afterlife in many verses, such as Qur'an 2:48, Qur'an 9:29, Qur'an 88:25-26 etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: The corpse is only washed and buried.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: All the corpses of the group members are buried at the cemetery.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic

activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Nigeria
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Nigeria
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Nigeria
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Nigeria
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Nigeria
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
– Yes [specify]: Power of creation and judging the activities of the members in the afterlife.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Nigeria
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Nothing escapes the knowledge of the supreme High God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme High God rewards good deeds in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme High God records evil against the wrongdoers to face the consequences in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The Supreme High God descend rainfall and changes the weather.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

In dreams:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The communication comes through revelation to messengers alone

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Other form of communication with living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Spirit's existence and presence make life possible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels and Jins are clear examples of the non-human supernatural beings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: Angels can only be seen when a person is dying.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

— Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not know human motives (What is in the mind).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: They are aware of Animals and Plants.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Jinns have a desire for food.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: A mysterious movement that humans could not understand.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Supernatural beings care about other creatures like humans, animals and plants.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: They punish evil-doers in the hereafter under the directives of Allah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Violating the rules of the High God leads to punishment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Angels punish evil-doers on the directives of the High God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: The greatest punishment is executed in the hereafter.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: Reward is only bestowed by the High God (Allah).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The Messiah is coming before the end of the world to save people from evil.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Alive, identified:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

Notes: The date of his coming is not known.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The Messiah is to save people from the evil.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group approved social norms prescribed by the Qur'an.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Every member must fast during the month of Ramadan.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: There is annual due of zakat on the properties of the wealthy members of the group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Members must spare time to attend daily congregational prayers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Members are to accept ethical guidance laid by the Qur'an.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Members perform extra obligatory prayers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 3

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Members attend weekly congregations on Fridays at the mosque.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 500

Notes: The congregation starts at a minimum of twelve members to an unrestricted maximum.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 168

Notes: 24 times 7, equals to 168 hours.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: Poverty relief is only through mutual assistance between the members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The group established Qur'anic schools to impart knowledge to their members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: The group members do not attend other schools apart from the Qur'anic schools.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: All efforts are made individually by the group members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Nigerian government provide transportation infrastructure for the general public in the region (group members inclusive).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: The group relied on the community leaders for the settlement of disputes and establishment of justice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not have a legal entity to execute institutionalized punishment in the region. They only exercise limited authority among the group members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Leaving of the group within the Nigeria subject the members to the institutionalized laws of the country.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The group used laws deduced directly from the Qur'an.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group is under the legal code of the country, even though, is out of their wish and consent.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: The government of the region did not allow any military institution out of its control, hence the group relied on limited effort to defend themselves against any threat.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group is under the shadow of the military institution of the Nigerian government.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: They only use the language of the Qur'an (Arabic).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group use other native languages of the region: Hausa, Fulani and English to some few.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group used some languages to communicate among themselves.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The group use the Hijrah lunar calendar for the timing of religious events and duties.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The calendar is meant for the general Muslim both Sunni, Shi'i and others under the religion.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The group cultivate lands to farm crops for their consumption.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Nigeria

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